

EOMORES

D3.5: Improved version of the algal forecasting models

WP3 – Innovative Service Component development

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I. Introduction

Within EOMORES, the models are an important part of the service components because many end-users operating within water quality simply collecting information (through in situ monitoring or otherwise) is not enough. They need to put the monitoring data into their water management day-to-day work. Part of that is the use of models to describe the ecosystem of water bodies and to indicate the threats, to fill gaps in their data analyses or use them in water management forecasts. This deliverable describes the models used in algal forecasting. The models were all developed by Deltares and are either based on Deltares' Delft3D software or data-driven. As such, they go from only forecasting at the monitoring location (Algae Radar) to a complete 3D vision of the water body (EWACS).

Development of the models will continue after EOMORES because new end-users have different requirements but the main reason is that water bodies are so diverse that sometimes new methods need to be developed. An example of this is the application of the Algae Radar in Lake Trasimeno (Italy) which required a different set up of the basic model than the set up used in lakes in the Netherlands.

This deliverable will first introduce the models (Chapter II). Chapter III will then show the results in the different pilots and where possible verification with monitoring data. The current version of this deliverable is a draft and not yet a finalised report.

II. The models

II.1. EWACS

II.1.1. Description

The EWACS model comprises of a hydrodynamic model (Delft3D Flow) for transportation of phytoplankton, a water quality model (D-WAQ) for administrating phytoplankton (and cyanobacteria) biomass (not necessarily for calculating growth) and the Ecofuzz model for scum appearance and disappearance (see Figure II-I).

Ecofuzz contains knowledge rules, or membership functions about scum formation and disappearance. Based on the values of the membership functions, the stability of the water column and the buoyancy capacity of the cyanobacteria are estimated. As input for the membership functions wind velocity, irradiation and time of day are used (see Figure II-II-Figure II-VI).

Figure II-I Representation of EWACS model with the coupled models and required inputs.

Figure II-II 'Appearance' and 'Disappearance' refer the appearance and disappearance of scums. Q = quantitative values; F = fuzzy values.

Windspeed for appearance of scums

Irradiation over the last 6 hours

Mean wind speed last hour	Irradiance flux last 6 h	Stability
Very high	high	low
Very high	moderate	low
Very high	low	moderate
High	high	low
High	moderate	low
High	low	moderate
Moderate	high	low
Moderate	moderate	moderate
Moderate	low	low
Low	high	very high
Low	moderate	very high
Low	low	high

Figure II-III knowledge rules about stability of the water column.

Irradiation over the last 6 hours

Time of the day

Irradiance flux last 6 h	Time of day	Buoyancy state
High	night	high
High	morning	high
High	early afternoon	moderate
High	late afternoon	low
High	evening	moderate
Moderate	night	high
Moderate	morning	high
Moderate	early afternoon	moderate
Moderate	late afternoon	moderate
Moderate	evening	moderate
Low	night	high
Low	morning	high
Low	early afternoon	moderate
Low	late afternoon	moderate
Low	evening	high

Figure II-IV knowledge rules about the algal buoyancy capacity.

Stability of the water column

buoyancy

Stability	Buoyancy	Degree of bloom formation
Low	high	low
Low	moderate	low
Low	low	very low
Moderate	high	moderate
Moderate	moderate	low
Moderate	low	low
High	high	very high
High	moderate	high
High	low	moderate
Very high	high	very high
Very high	moderate	high
Very high	low	moderate

Figure II-V knowledge rules about the degree of bloom formation.

Figure II-VI knowledge rules about scum disappearance.

II.1.2. History

In the late 1990's the EcoFuzz model was developed to predict the appearance and disappearance of cyanobacterial surface blooms (Ibelings et al., 2003). Using fuzzy modelling, the model was used to describe three governing conditions for surface bloom formation:

1. presence of exiting cyanobacterial population
2. cell buoyancy
3. water column stability

In the paper of Ibelings et al. (2003), the EcoFuzz model was combined with a water transport model and applied to lake IJsselmeer: the largest fresh water lake of Western Europe. The results were promising, but only reflected open water scum formation and not scum formation in sheltered places.

In 2008, Ecofuzz was combined with a hydrodynamic and water quality model, which combination was given the name EWACS (Early Warning Against sCumS). EWACS was applied to four lakes with the aim to developing the model into a real time forecasting early warning system. Although the model showed good results for two lakes, the results for the two other lakes were disappointing. Even though field data was collected, this data could not help explaining the mismatch between field data and model results.

From 2014 onwards, with increased data availability from remote sensing (satellites) and WISP (hand held device for spectral measurements), new attempts were made to improve EWACS. Therefore, EWACS was applied to three Dutch lakes. The model results for lake Delftse Hout and Westeinderplassen was improved by adapting the transport rate of the scums (Delftse Hout) and changing the scum appearance and disappearance probabilities (Westeinderplassen). For the third lake (Paterswoldsemeer) only comparisons were made between field data and model result (Figure II-VII). No in-depth analyses were performed.

II.1.3. Aim

The aim in EOMORES is to improve the EWACS modeling tool applied to lake PWM on basis of data from various sources. PWM has a bathing area along the southeastern edge of the lake.

Figure II-VII satellite image from lake PWM (left panel) and EWACS results before improvement in EOMORES (right panel) for 01/08/2014 combined with monitoring data (filled circles). Orange filled circles indicate an observed scum and blue filled circles no observed scum. The color bar represents the concentration of scums simulated by EWACS (low to high).

II.2. BLOOM 'stand-alone' mode (BSA)

II.2.1. Description

BLOOM is an algal model focusing on species competition and adaptation to different limiting factors in the environment. It can be used to calculate species composition, algal growth and primary production. Algae types that are included in BLOOM are greens (green algae, freshwater); 3 cyanobacteria genera: *Aphanizomenon* (harmful, freshwater), *Microcystis* (harmful, freshwater), *Oscillatoria* (filamentous, fresh water); diatoms (both freshwater and marine); flagellates (a mixture of small marine algae with flagella); dinoflagellates (marine); *Phaeocystis* (harmful, marine); and *Ulva* (macroalgae, both freshwater and marine).

The BLOOM model is unique in its kind because it is using an optimization approach. Every time step the model calculates the algal species composition that leads to maximum growth given the available nutrient resources and amount of energy. Species can also be limited by growth or mortality, if conditions are optimal or insufficient to grow, respectively. Model results well capture natural patterns and phenomena. These include opportunistic fast growing (r-strategy) species dominating when light and nutrient availability are high, while more specialized but slower growing (k-strategy) species will dominate under less favourable conditions.

BLOOM is part of the water quality module (D-WAQ) of the Delft3D software suite. Typically, BLOOM is used as part of a comprehensive ecosystem model, consisting of all relevant water quality processes from D-WAQ and a proper (0D/1D/2D/3D) hydrodynamic model. Such ecosystem model can predict algal growth and composition on basis of meteorological data and the relevant loadings (nutrients, silt, etc) into the system. However, full ecosystem models require relatively much effort to set up, calibrate, and validate. Even when the hydrodynamic model is simplified to for instance a 0D box model, the water quality model will still require quantitative data on the nutrient inputs into the system, as well as on the various components affecting the underwater light climate. Often, these data are lacking, as is especially often the case for smaller freshwater lakes.

In such cases BLOOM in 'stand-alone' mode (BSA) may provide a solution. BLOOM in stand-alone mode will still predict algal growth and composition, but it based on fewer water quality processes, and only requires total nutrient concentrations as input. It has various advantageous over the default mode:

- Instead of the total nutrient *inputs* into the system, it only requires the total nutrient *concentrations* that are present in the water. Data on nutrient concentrations are much more often available than are nutrient inputs.
- As it involves only few processes (and hence parameters), calibration is relatively quick and easy. Often, calibration involves parameters affecting the light climate or P-adsorption, which parameters can later on be used in a full ecosystem model as well.
- The model will quickly show whether measured nutrient concentrations are in agreement with the measured chlorophyll levels; quite often this is not the case. For instance, the measured amount of phosphor in the water may be way too low to support the measured algal biomass. Such inconsistencies points out errors in the data. As such, the tool can be used as a data consistency test.
- Once calibrated, the model will tell you which environmental factors are limiting algal growth, thus providing more insight in the system and how to effectively manage it.

BLOOM in stand-alone mode can thus be considered an easy stepping stone to improve your system understanding, to perform a data consistency check, and to calibrate of the model with respect to the light climate. There are however also a few disadvantages:

- Its dependency on total nutrient concentrations allows limited options for carrying out predictions into the future, or for testing various scenarios or management measures.
- Also, the stand-alone tool can only be run in a 0D box model. This means that it cannot be run well in combination with a spatially explicit hydrodynamic model. Of course, some horizontal heterogeneity can still be captured by running a series of independent 0D box models with environmental settings that correspond to different locations in the system.

II.2.2. Aim

Within the EOMORES project, the BLOOM stand-alone model was tested for lake PWM and lake Twiske.

II.3. Algae Radar

II.3.1. Introduction

Although the Netherlands is a small country, it has more than 600 bathing locations, mainly around inland water bodies. More than 90% of these water bodies have at least a good water quality status (Environmental indicator report 2018). This water quality status is based on the concentrations of E.coli and enterococci bacteria. However, the bathing water locations suffer more from cyanobacteria (blue-green algae) than from E.coli and enterococci. Every year a large portion of these locations needs to issue health warnings to the public or even shut the location due to the occurrence of cyanobacteria. This led to the need of water managers for a forecasting model that was able to predict scum formation at bathing water locations. The model developed for that need was EWACS (see Chapter III.1). Although for certain locations EWACS showed good results, this was not the case in all tested sites due to a number of reasons (some mentioned in Chapter IV), including the data input for the model. Furthermore, EWACS is a 3D model and is therefore an expensive model to build for new locations. EWACS was also designed mainly for water managers and is currently not suitable to be used by other stakeholders. This led Deltares in 2015/2016 to come up with a different type of forecasting model that should meet the conditions of relatively cheap, quick information provider, forecasting several bathing water locations at the same time and be useful for many different stakeholders. The outcome was the development of the Algae Radar (Figure II-VIII). Unlike EWACS, the Algae Radar is not based on the Delft3D software but strictly a data-driven model. For the future, the aim is to apply the Algae Radar to regions that contain several bathing water locations. Until now, Deltares has been working on improving the model itself using individual locations as pilots including three locations in EOMORES: Lake Twiske, Paterswoldsemeer and Trasimeno. Data modelling within the Algae Radar consists of two steps, construction of a basic and an adaptive model.

Figure II-VIII Algae Radar logo.

II.3.2. Basic model

In this step, chl-a concentrations are calculated as a function of meteorological variables (wind speed, irradiation and air temperature). One of the reasons to use these variables is their high frequency monitoring. These data are obtained from nearby meteo stations at airports. Another reason is that these variables are also forecasted at these stations by the Met Office. In situ data,

such as nutrients, pH and oxygen are not measured at high frequency and therefore (currently) not suitable to be used in our model. Chlorophyll-a of cyanobacteria is also not measured at high frequency by water boards (usually once every two weeks). The relationship of chl-a with the meteorological variables in the model can be described as follows:

$$Chl_{cyanobacteria} = aT + bRad + cWind$$

Here, T is the air temperature (°C), Rad the irradiation (J cm⁻²) and Wind is wind speed (m s⁻¹). The coefficients a, b and c are used to adjust the model calibrated using least squares regression. They have different weights which differ for each location and temporally. As such, the equation becomes as follows:

$$Chl_{cyanobacteria}(t) = a_1T(t-t_1) + a_2T(t-t_2) + \dots + a_NT(t-t_N) + b_1Rad(t-t_1) + b_2Rad(t-t_2) + \dots + b_NRad(t-t_N) + c_1Wind(t-t_1) + c_2Wind(t-t_2) + \dots + c_NWind(t-t_N)$$

The result is a continuous prediction of Chl-a with seasonal variation influenced by meteorology.

II.3.3. Adaptive model

The results for modelled chl-a concentrations in the basic model may deviate from observations due to processes in the real world (e.g. nutrient dynamics, zooplankton predation) that are not included in the model or due to restoration measures. To overcome this, an adaptive step is included in which a Kalman filter is applied. The prediction obtained with the basic model is improved to a prediction $Pred^*_t$ by applying:

$$Pred^*_t = R_{t-1}.Pred_t + Uncertainty^C_t$$

The correction factor R is itself updated every time by applying:

$$R_t = \gamma R_{t-1} + 1 - \gamma + Uncertainty^R_t$$

These uncertainties are determined by:

$$Uncertainty^C_t = a.Uncertainty^C_{t-1} + b.Rand$$

$$Uncertainty^R_t = c.Uncertainty^R_{t-1} + d.Rand$$

Implementation of the adaptive model is as follows:

To be able to predict cyanobacterial levels in the current year the adaptive model uses the weights that have been calibrated in advance with data from previous years. As soon as an actual measurement, M, of cyano-chlorophyll at time t_n is obtained it is then compared with the prediction for time t_n . The coefficients a-d are then adapted in order to minimize:

$$\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{n=1}^N M_{t_n} - Pred^*_{t_n}}$$

This exercise is repeated every time a new measurement is obtained. Without new measurements R_t over time converges back to 1.

III. Results EWACS

III.1. Aim and approach

Aim was to improve the application of the EWACS model for lake PWM. In a stepwise manner, several aspects were calibrated/validated:

- algae and scum transport;
- water column stability and scum (dis) appearance;
- sensitivity to wind;
- ECOFUZZ membership functions

To this end the following data sources were used:

- WISP (spectral measurements, handheld device), providing data on:
 - Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a), cyano-phycoyanin (CPC), suspended particulate matter (SPM) and extinction coefficient of water (kd) for several lake locations in (summer half year) 2014.
 - Logging of scum presence and absence for 2014. However, not systematically or consistently reported.
- EcoWatch (spectral measurements, fixed location), providing data on:
 - Chl-a, CPC, SPM and kd measurements for several periods in 2016, 2017 and 2018.
 - Color photos for several instances in 2016.
- Remote Sensing data, providing data on:
 - Converted Sentinel-2 (S2) images with a 10m x 10m resolution. This means that near shore and small scums cannot be detected.
 - 9 images for 2016, of which 2 only partial.
- Meteorological data on station Eelde, providing data on:

Temperature, insolation, wind direction and wind speed, at 10 min time intervals.

III.2. Results and discussion

III.2.1. Algae and scum transport

The 2014 EWACS runs (e.g. Figure III-I right panel) showed that Chl-a concentrations were highest near the shores. Analysis showed that this is mainly the result of the scum transport function: once

scums have been formed, they are picked up by and transported in the direction of the wind. The model results on 9 am and 1 pm (Figure III-II) indicate that scums have both temporal and spatial dynamics. Comparing these two figures with the presence and absence of scums (Figure III-III), it shows that it depends on the time of the day and the location whether model results and observations are in agreement, but nevertheless the model gives an approximation of where to expect scums.

Figure III-I EWACS output on Chl-a and measured Chl-a concentrations on 01/08/2014, 09:00:00 and 12:00 (blue color indicates low chlorophyll concentrations, other colors indicate high concentrations).

Figure III-II EWACS scum results (colors indicated low scum values (blue) and higher scums values (every other color) on 01/08/2014, at 09:00 (left panel) and 13:00 (right panel).

Figure III-III EWACS scum results (blue colors indicate low scum values, other colors indicate higher scums values) validated against observed presence and absence of scums (orange and blue circles, respectively), on 01/08/2014.

Noticeable on these figures is the very pronounced spatial pattern in the algal distribution. It seems that the transport of phytoplankton and cyanobacteria is faster and more pronounced in the model than in reality. For example on the first of August, Chl-a concentrations are piling up along the shoreline, while relative high concentrations are also measured more off shore (Figure III-I right panel). Moreover, because of wind transport, Chl-a concentrations can change quickly (see middle and right figure).

The low Chl-a concentrations in the middle of the lake can be explained by the worst case assumption in EWACS that all of the measured Chl-a belonged to cyanobacteria. During a scum formation episode, a high percentage (40-100%) of this cyanobacterial biomass is transported to the top layer of the model. A wind transport function then transports these scums relatively fast to the edges of the lake.

In order to improve its spatial patterns, the model was recalibrated on basis of S2 images (Figure III-IV). Note that elevated Chl-a concentrations in the S2 images do not necessarily mean 'scums'. These figures suggest that wind speeds of 3 m/s or more mix the lake, with only some elevated Chl-a concentrations remaining near the shores. Also, the wind direction seems to determine on which shores the elevated Chl-a concentrations end up.

Since there are no S2 images for 2014, a EWACS model simulation for the year 2016 was performed. In this simulation, only 50% of the phytoplankton biomass is assumed to be cyanobacterial. Model results are shown in Figure III-V. The mixing of the lake by higher wind velocities, as seen in the S2 images, is not simulated by EWACS. Figure III-V (left panel) shows the result of Chl-a concentrations patterns at a wind velocity of 6 m/s. Model results based on lower wind velocities (middle panel) seem to resemble the image slightly better, but still no chlorophyll remains in the middle of the lake. When reducing the additional transport speed of scums, however, an improved pattern appears.

Figure III-IV S2 Snapshots of lake PWM at different wind conditions in 2016.

Figure III-V Chl-a concentrations on 29/07/16, with a wind velocity of 6 m/s and the default scum transport speed (left panel), with a wind velocity of 2 m/s and the default scum transport speed (middle panel), with a wind velocity of 2 m/s and 10% of the default scum transport speed (right panel).

III.2.2. Water column stability and scum (dis)appearance

The simulated timing of scum appearances and disappearances were validated by comparing the pictures taken by the EcoWatch to episodes of the simulated chance on scum appearance and disappearance (see Figure III-VI). These figures show that (un)stable water column conditions are

picked up by EWACS. However, in the EcoWatch pictures there was no instance on which a scum could be visually confirmed, although EWACS did simulate episodes of high chance on scum formation. Also, Chl-a concentrations measured by the EcoWatch could not confirm scums in the early morning of for example the 31/07 and the 2/08 (see Table III-I). Noticeable were the unexpected high Chl-a concentrations (indicator of scum formation) by the EcoWatch on the 27/07, when EWACS simulated high chance on scum disappearance and the EcoWatch picture show unstable water column conditions.

All in all, based on the EcoWatch pictures, there seems to be an agreement between actual and simulated water column stability. However, the available data could not confirm whether scum formation took place or not.

Table III-I overview of Chl-a concentrations (three hour mean, $\mu\text{g/l}$) on the date and time the pictures on the left were taken.

Date	3hr mean EcoWatch data
27-Jul	197
31-Jul	no data
01-Aug	45
02-Aug	no data

Figure III-VI chance of scum appearance (green line) and disappearance (blue line) simulated by EWACS. Below, pictures taken by the EcoWatch and matched to date and time of the EWACS simulation.

III.2.3. Wind sensitivity

A data-analysis of local wind conditions at PWM (bathing area) and the wind conditions at the meteorological station Eelde highlighted that the local wind conditions may differ from the wind conditions at the meteorological station (Figure III-VII). This may lead to different hydrodynamics (transport patterns and vertical mixing) but also means that many of the values used for the membership functions of Ecofuzz are not accurate.

Figure III-VII Wind speed (m/s, left panel) and wind direction (degrees, right panel): local measurements (x-axis) against measurements at the meteorological station (y-axis).

To get insight in how sensitive the hydrodynamic simulations are for wind speed and directions in terms of flow patterns, a series of tracer simulations were carried out. A tracer run is a model simulation in which parcels of water are labelled and are followed during the course of the simulation.

Five tracer simulations were carried out in which a tracer was released in the southwestern or southeastern corner of the lake:

- The reference situation
- Wind direction changed by + 20 degrees
- Wind direction changed by - 20 degrees
- Wind speed changed by + 20%
- Wind speed changed by – 20%

The tracer simulations for the reference situation (Figure III-VIII) illustrate that a scum produced in the south western part of the lake, may end up at de bathing water area (south eastern part of the lake) (Figure III-VIII upper panels). Tracers released in the bathing area, can linger there quite a while, depending on wind direction and speed (Figure III-VIII lower panels). It can thus be concluded that scums in the bathing area may result from local production as well as from transport processes.

Figure III-VIII Reference run at different moments in time and when releasing a tracer in the southwestern part of the lake (upper panels) and when releasing a tracer in the southeastern part of the lake (lower panels).

In all cases shown in Figure III-IX, a tracer has been released in the south western part of the lake. The figures show that changes in either wind direction or speed altered the water transport patterns. An anticlockwise turn of 20 degrees (left upper figure) transported the tracer more north, while a clockwise rotation of 20 degrees (right upper figure) transported the tracer towards the bathing area.

Changes in wind speed had a less pronounced effect on the tracer. A 20% decrease in wind speed (lower left figure) transported the tracer less far, while a 20% increase in wind speed (lower right figure) split the tracer into a northern and southern part.

Furthermore, the tracer simulations showed that the lake is reasonably well mixed: regardless from its starting location, a tracer got mixed within 3 to 4 days. Also, results suggest (again) that the extra wind drag on phytoplankton and cyanobacteria overestimates their transport to the edges of the lake, thereby clearing most of the lake of cyanobacterial biomass. As a result, no scum appearances are predicted in those areas. This was already discussed in the section on algae and scum transport above (section IV.2.1).

Figure III-IX Results at 06/06 06:00 when a tracer was released in the south western part of the lake at various wind directions or speeds. Left upper panel: Wind direction minus 20 degrees; right upper panel: Wind direction plus 20 degrees; Lower left panel: Wind speed minus 20%; Lower right panel: Wind speed plus 20%.

III.2.4. ECOFUZZ membership functions

To test the default applicability of the Ecofuzz membership functions, Ecofuzz results were validated separate from the rest of the EWACS model.

First, the 2014 data on presence and absence of scums were used to test whether Ecofuzz simulates scum appearance and disappearance at the right moments. During the analyses, attention was also paid to individual monitoring locations (Figure III-X) to see if some stations are consistently in (dis)agreement with the Ecofuzz results.

Second, the 2016 data of the ECOWATCH were used to look for agreement between ECOWATCH data and Ecofuzz. Furthermore, for 2016 more data, like % cyanobacteria, chl-a concentrations, and wind speed and direction were used to look for a correlation between scum (dis)appearance in field observations and simulations results.

Figure III-X Measurement locations.

From the data (not shown) it can be concluded that there were only scum observations near the shores. Figure III-XI shows the results for scum presence and absence for all locations in 2014. Some observations:

- The amount of measured locations per measuring round varied considerably, possibly obscuring the analysis.
- If a scum is present, this is mostly the case for just a few locations (spatial variability).
- Scums are never present on all locations simultaneously.

Figure III-XI scum presence and absence for all locations in 2014.

In May (Figure III-XII upper panel), only on one location (location 14) a scum was observed (twice). The first scum observation at this location does not align with Ecofuzz results (low chance of scum formation). The second scum observation at this location is in line with Ecofuzz results. However, the by Ecofuzz predicted scum forming episodes were not reflected by the field data. Reasons for mismatch can be a low phytoplankton biomass (e.g. due to zooplankton grazing, start of growing season of phytoplankton (but is quite late)), or failing of logging all the scum presences. Because in PWM many sheltered locations exist, an underestimation of good conditions of scum formation was expected, not an overestimation.

At the start of August (Figure III-XII middle panel), Ecofuzz and field data were in agreement, which is also the case in some of the other episodes of scums presence, although less pronounced as only for a few stations scum presence was reported. Interesting were also the events of no observed scums while Ecofuzz suggested that there should be some scums left: there was a high chance on scum formation and the chance on disappearance of scums was limited.

In September (Figure III-XII lower panel) it remains questionable if all scum observations were logged, as no single scum was reported and Ecofuzz predicts quite a few episodes of scum formation and less episodes of scum disappearance. If the absence of scums is correct, this may suggest that the internal turbulence in this month is larger than expected.

Figure III-XII Scum appearance (red) and disappearance (grey) as predicted by the model and the number of locations in which a scum was observed (green dots), in three different months (may, august, September).

The knowledge rules used in EcoFuzz do not systematically match the logged scum presences: EcoFuzz overestimates the instances of scum formation. Reasons for this could be: zooplankton grazing in May, higher turbulence than expected based on the knowledge rules, inconsistent logging of scum observations.

Given the Ecofuzz results, it is likely EWACS will overestimate the episodes of scum formation and also the intensity of the scums. No univocal clues are apparent for improving Ecofuzz membership functions.

To illuminate the mismatch between the Ecofuzz data and observed presence and absence of scums, the high frequency data of the EcoWatch was analysed (Figure III-XIII and Figure III-XIV). The EcoWatch data does not provide real presence or absence of scums, but very high values of Chl-a are good indications of a scum drifting by. Moreover, in 2016, a considerable amount of color photos, taken by the EcoWatch, are available and may be useful for validation whether the high Chl-a

concentrations were indeed scums. Additionally, the in situ data in the vicinity of the EcoWatch also provides the share of blue-greens of the total amount of phytoplankton cells, hinting at episodes of scum formation.

Figure III-XIII Scum appearance (red) and disappearance (grey) as predicted by the model and various variables measured by the EcoWatch in June 2016. Chlfa means chlorophyll-a.

Figure III-XIV Scum appearance (red) and disappearance (grey) as predicted by the model and various variables measured by the EcoWatch in June 2016 in July 2016. Chlfa means chlorophyll-a.

Although the data measured by the EcoWatch and modeled by EcoFuzz did comply with each other sometimes, this was certainly not always the case (Figure III-XIII). Compliance seemed to occur when the share of blue green algae were at least 30%. But this was observed just two times: more data is needed to be able to validate this hypothesis. No conclusive correlations were found to couple high chl-a concentrations (EcoWatch) or scum predictions (Ecofuzz) to any of the variable that were taken into account. Difficulties in linking meteorological data to high Chl-a concentrations, as observed by the EcoWatch, may stem from both local production and transport. Another difficulty is the very local measuring scope of the EcoWatch: a scum may drive by near the EcoWatch, but remain unobserved.

Also looking at the results of July 2016 (pictures available from 27/07 onwards, Figure III-XIV), there is no clear agreement between in situ data and scum appearance, although biomass seems to increase during the period when EcoFuzz predicts a longer period of scum formation. However, on

31/01, where EcoFuzz scum appearance predicts, the pictures do not indicate any trace of scums (see picture below).

To conclude, based on the 2014 scum observation data and the 2016 EcoWatch data it cannot be pinpointed why Ecofuzz results and observed presence of scums differ. The complexity of scum formation and disappearance, the probably high heterogeneity of the lake (for example wind) and the sparse and/or incomplete data does not allow for understanding how scum formation in PWM works and hence how to improve Ecofuzz' memberships functions based on the available data.

III.3. Conclusions

The test case for PWM shows that the EWACS model can be improved by calibration/validation of its various constituents on basis of local data. Probably, the findings are also valid for other applications of the EWACS model. Main findings are the following:

- The transport and mixing of cyanobacteria: simulated phytoplankton and cyanobacterial biomass is not in line with the S2 data. This can be explained by the worst-case assumption that all biomass consists of blue-green algae, and by the speed with which scums are transported within the model.
- Sensitivity to wind: mismatches for hydrodynamics and scum (dis)appearance may be caused by differences between measured meteorological conditions (especially wind velocity and direction) and the actual wind velocity and direction conditions at the lake. Pictures taken by the EcoWatch suggest that the water column stability is in line between observations and model.
- Mismatches between predicted and observed scum presence and absence by ECOFUZZ may be caused by a wrong timing of simulated scum (dis)appearance (membership functions, minimum of required biomass for scum formation) and/or inconsistent logging of the presence or absence of scums. Further clarification requires a more systematical and consistent logging of scum presence and absence in combination with local wind speed and direction. Obviously, the mismatches of EcoFuzz are conveyed also to EWACS, explaining (also part of) the mismatches between EWACS results and S2 and WISP data.

IV. Results Bloom stand-alone mode

IV.1. Results BLOOM stand-alone Lake PWM

IV.1.1. Aim and approach

Aim of this activity was to find out whether the high cyanobacteria occurrences in 2016 could be ascribed to environmental conditions (nutrient levels, temperature and irradiation). More specifically, it was studied whether it is possible to disentangle *local production* from *transportation* of scums. While the BLOOM stand-alone can well capture the first (production), it is a 0D box model and can thus not deal with spatial heterogeneity or lateral transport. The result will thus inform us of the applicability of the tool in the case of PWM. Also, the results may help to direct management

measures to prevent scums appearing in the bathing area (e.g. changing local conditions vs refraining scums to reach the bathing area).

IV.1.2. Data analysis

A data analysis on long term PWM in situ data (nutrients, oxygen, suspended matter, chl-a, Secchi depth) of the bathing area shows that over the last five years in PWM the concentrations of total nitrogen and phosphorus and their dissolved fractions near the bathing area are decreasing. The seasonal pattern of NO_3 and PO_4 are comparable (Figure IV-1): higher from autumn to spring and around detection limits during summer. This indicates nutrient limitation of phytoplankton growth. However, total P increases in July and August, indicating phosphorus loading of the lake and thus loosening P limitation for phytoplankton (note that this increase becomes less pronounced in the more recent years).

Chl-a concentrations are highest between July and September, but are declining over the more recent years. This coincides with the period in which, on general, temperatures are highest (profitable for phytoplankton growth in general), wind speeds are lowest, and higher TotN and TotP concentrations (profitable for specifically cyanobacteria).

Figure IV-1 Monthly averaged values for several water quality parameters measured near the bathing area. Data are depicted for the years 2011-2016. The darker blue colors represent earlier years and the lighter blue colors more recent years.

IV.1.3. BSA model setup

BSA assumes a part of N and P is refractory bound and therefore not available to phytoplankton. The refractory fractions have default values (0.75 mg/l for N and 0.03 mg/l for P) and are based on data analyses of hyper trophic lakes. However, in less eutrophic lakes it is plausible that these fractions are smaller, as the relative importance of processes may change (e.g. decomposition of detritus, uptake rates of nutrients). This is also the case in PWM, as the default value of refractory bound N and P are often equal or larger than the measured total N and P concentrations. Therefore, a quick calibration of measured Chl-a and inorganic N and P concentrations resulted in refractory bound N defined as “ $0.90 \cdot N_{tot} - 0.38$ ” and refractory bound P as “ $0.97 \cdot P_{tot} - 0.01$ ”.

For light climate, BSA uses the extinction coefficient. This is measured by the ECOWatch. The in situ measured Secchi depth was converted to extinction using $1.7 / \text{Secchi depth}$. The BSA results for ECOWatch and in situ derived extinction were similar.

IV.1.4. Results

BSA model results for chlorophyll and species composition are shown in Figure IV-II. The model predicts a local species composition without blue greens, probably related to the locally low nutrient concentrations (Figure IV-II).

Figure IV-II upper panel: Chl-a concentrations in 2016 at the bathing location: red cross modelled, black triangle measured Chl-a; lower panel: Modelled species composition: red squares represents diatoms, orange triangles flagellates, green circles green and blue diamonds cyanobacteria.

IV.1.5. Discussion and conclusions

Results suggest that the scums observed in the bathing area may be produced at another part of the lake. Management measures to prevent scums appearing in the bathing area should thus not only focus on the local conditions, but also take measures in other locations and/or refrain scums to reach the bathing area.

The finding that the scums in the bathing area could also be produced elsewhere in the lake, limits the applicability of the BSA tool, since the tool does not take into account heterogeneity or transport within a lake. To solve this, the tool could be applied to various sub regions within the lake. This would however require monitoring data on those various sub regions as well.

IV.2. Results BLOOM stand-alone Lake Twiske

IV.2.1. Aim and approach

Aim for lake Twiske was to find out whether the high algal bloom events could be ascribed to extra water discharges during dry periods. Underlying idea is that these extra water discharges contain relatively high nutrient concentrations. If these water discharges indeed turn out to be relevant, the Algalradar-tool for lake Twiske could be extended by including a relation to droughts (or to nutrient concentration). Approach was to simulate lake Twiske over multiple years and find out to what extent the algae are limited by nutrients.

IV.2.2. Model setup

Input variables of the BSA model are:

1. Total concentrations of nutrients (based on available WFD-measurements)
2. Water temperature (based on available WFD-measurements)
3. Solar irradiation (based on daily averaged irradiation data from KNMI in units of w/m^2);

Calibration variables of the BSA model are:

1. Depth.
2. Depth is a calibration variable since the effective mixing depth of the algae varies per system, location and time. Actual or measured depths may serve to validate the calibrated value. For WFD monitoring location BDV044 depth-measurements can be found on www.hnk-water.nl.
3. Background extinction/Suspended matter concentration
4. Background extinction was used to calibrate the turbidity.

Validation variables in the BSA are:

1. Chlorophyll concentrations and cyanobacterial concentrations (based on the results of the swimming water monitoring).
2. Data on the algal species composition throughout the year (based on the WFD-measurements).
3. Total extinction or turbidity.

4. Data or information on the total extinction of light may serve as validation (based on the WFD measurements of Secchi depth or suspended matter, although extinction measures are a more direct (and thus preferred) measure).
5. Species composition (based on the results of the swimming water monitoring).

IV.2.3. Model calibration

First, the concentration of suspended matter was set to 30 mg/l, to obtain a correct maximum transparency (500 cm).

Secondly, the depth was set to 20m: although the depth at the monitoring location BDV044 is about 30m deep, the local situation is being influenced by water from surrounding areas (with shallower depths). Also, in summer stratification frequently occurs, during which periods the effective depth is decreased. At a chosen depth of 20m the (timing and level of the) algal blooms as well as the nutrient concentrations (especially during the summer) show most agreement with the measurements.

IV.2.4. Results

Results for location BDV044 in lake Twiske for the years 2010-2017 are shown in the Figure IV-III- Figure IV-VII; these figures show measured and predicted values for:

- Nitrate
- Phosphate
- Secchi Depth
- Chlorophyll
- Factors limiting algal growth

Based on these graphs the model seems to predict the timing and intensity of the bloom quite well. Main discrepancy between model and measurements occurs in summer time, where nitrate levels seem over-estimated by the model.

Figure IV-VIII shows the predicted and measured chlorophyll per phytoplankton group for the years 2010-2018. Note that only for the last year (2018) measured was available for the (central) location BDV044; other measurements were taken at surrounding locations along the shorelines of Twiske. As a result, the comparison is less suitable for evaluating the model performance. Yet, the model seems to capture the main patterns of algal succession fairly well, with diatoms being the first to appear, and blue greens occurring mainly in the second part of the summer.

Figure IV-IX shows the predicted and measured chlorophyll per phytoplankton group in 2018. Both measurements and predictions correspond to location BDV044. A true validation remains difficult due to the small number of data points in this location.

Graph for location BLM Column, BDV044

Figure IV-III Nitrate concentrations (mgN/l) in location BDV044 in lake Twiske on basis of BSA model predictions (blue lines) and in-situ measurements (pink dots).

Graph for location BLM Column, BDV044

Figure IV-IV Phosphate concentrations (mgP/l) in location BDV044 in lake Twiske on basis of BSA model predictions (blue lines) and in-situ measurements (pink dots).

Graph for location BLM Column, BDV044

Figure IV-V Secchi depth in location BDV044 in lake Twiske on basis of BSA model predictions (blue lines) and in-situ measurements (pink dots, named ZICHT (water board terminology)).

Complex graph

Figure IV-VI Chlorophyll concentrations ($\mu\text{g/l}$) in location BDV044 in lake Twiske on basis of BSA model predictions (blue lines) and in-situ measurements (pink dots).

Graph for location BLM Column

Figure IV-VII Factors limiting algal growth in location BDV044 in lake Twiske on basis of BSA model predictions. Colors indicate the various factors considered: nitrate (red); light (orange); phosphate (yellow); silicate (grey). A value of 1 indicates a factor is limiting. To facilitate visual inspection, the various factors were stacked in the graph.

Figure IV-VIII Chlorophyll concentrations (ug/l) per phytoplankton group as predicted by the model (curved lines) and on basis of in-situ measurements (dots): diatoms (red); cyanobacteria (blue); greens (green). Note that the model predictions correspond to location BDV044, while the measurements were taken in more shallow locations along the shore. Only for the last year (2018) the measurements were taken in location BDV044.

Figure IV-IX Chlorophyll concentrations (ug/l) per phytoplankton group as predicted by the model (curved lines) and on basis of in-situ measurements (dots): diatoms (red); cyanobacteria (blue); greens (green). Note that for this year both the model predictions and the measurements correspond to location BDV044.

IV.2.5. Discussion and conclusions

Model results suggest that the system is mostly not limited by nutrients. Nutrient limitations occur sometimes at the end of the spring bloom, sometimes at the end of the summer, but not in all years, and only for relatively short periods. According to the model, light is the most dominant factor limiting algal growth. This suggests that stratification and the presence of suspended matter have a larger influence on the timing and intensity of the BLOOM than nutrients have. If this is correct, this would mean that additional nutrients would not lead to more, or more frequent, cyanobacteria blooms. This thus limits the suspected role of the extra water discharges in causing harmful blooms.

A possible explanation for the idea that the extra water discharges could initiate or enhance algal blooms, could be due to a 'cofounding factor': during periods of warm weather there may be little rain, which leads to a rain deficit, leading to (the need for) extra water discharges. However, during periods of warm weather also stratification may occur, which leads to a smaller mixing depth and thus to a decrease in the light limitation. It could thus well be that the occurrence of algal blooms takes place at the same time as the extra water discharges, although no (causal) relation exists between the two.

It should however be noted that the model seems to overestimate nitrate concentrations in summer. As a result, it could under predict the role of nitrate as a limiting factor. Also, the model does not take into account spatial heterogeneity. It is calibrated to represent the center of lake Twiske, and therefore does not represent the surrounding more shallow bathing areas. It could thus be that conditions at those other locations are different, and that nitrate could be more (often)

limiting in those locations. Testing the limiting factors in those surrounding locations with the BSA tool would require measurements at those locations and possibly a re-calibration. Alternatively, a more comprehensive 2D or 3D model could be set up. Though setting up such a model would require relatively much effort, it would cover all relevant locations at once, including the (water, nutrient, and algae) transports between them.

V. Results Algae Radar

V.1. Paterswoldsemeer

Within EOMORES the modelling exercises within WP3 are all hindcasts. As such, the results presented for the Algae Radar do not show confidence limits on the model results because we worked with actual measured meteo data instead of meteo forecasts.

For the Paterswoldsemeer the Algae Radar was calibrated for the years 2010-2016 and the cyano-chlorophyll concentrations for 2017 were predicted and verified with the in situ measurements. Because it is difficult to quantify a deviation between modelled and measured cyano-chlorophyll (i.e. how much deviation is acceptable?) the modelled and measured results were verified within the health levels of the Dutch Bathing Water protocol for cyanobacteria (Figure V-1). This protocol uses three levels of health risk (no, slight and severe risk) that are related to cyano-chlorophyll concentrations (<12.5, 12.5-75 and > 75 µg/L, respectively). Modelled results were compared to measured cyano-chlorophyll concentrations by counting the amount of times that both results were within the same health risk level.

In 2017, a total of 36 in situ measurements were performed between 3 January and 31 October. There are therefore 36 occasions where model and measurements can be compared to each other.

Figure V-I Cyanobacteria protocol for bathing water of the Netherlands (http://cyanobacterien.stowa.nl/upload/blauwalgenprotocol_2012.pdf)

Figure V-II shows the results of the basic and adaptive model of the Algae Radar in the Paterswoldsemeer for 2017. As is normal, the basic model (top panel) shows deviations from measurements because this model only considers meteorological variables. The adaptive model (second panel) provides much better results because it uses the Kalman filter to correct predictions for incoming measurements. The results of the adaptive model are shown in Table V-I. The table shows that the Algae Radar had a score of 83% correct predictions.

Figure V-II Algae Radar results for Paterswoldsemeer. The top panel shows the results of the basic model (red line) and in situ measurements (blue dots). The second panel shows the results of the adaptive model. The third panel is the same as the second panel but only with model results (red dots) at times when a measurement (blue dots) was performed. The fourth panel shows the correction factor that was applied within the adaptive model (see Chapter III.4.3) to correct model results at a given time for a measurement.

Table V-I Comparison between modeled and measured data on cyano-chlorophyll concentrations for 2017 in the Paterswoldsemeer. Modeled and measured data were counted how often they were within the same health risk level of the Cyanobacteria protocol (Figure V-I).

Correct predictions	Wrong predictions	Total
30	6	36

V.2. Twiske

The Algae Radar was in 2018 applied to seven bathing water locations in 't Twiske (Figure V-III). For these locations, the model was trained for the years 2010-2017 and predicted 2018. Model results for 2018 were verified with in situ measurements of the water board in the same way as described in Chapter V.1.

Figure V-III Bathing water locations in 't Twiske (Netherlands). The Algae Radar was applied to seven of these locations: De Does, 't Vennegat, De Leers, Schoorl strand, Wezenlijk strand, Kure Jan strand and Speelsloot.

Figure V-IV - Figure V-X show the results of the Algae Radar predictions in 2018 for the seven bathing water locations and Table V-II shows how often model and measurements were in the same health warning level (see Chapter V.1 for an explanation). The amount of data to verify the predictions is not high. When the cyanobacteria grow without a sudden increase then the Algae Radar predictions are in the same range as the measurements. Deviations from the measurements occur when there is a quick increase in biomass in the field followed by a sudden decrease in the following measurement. The Algae Radar has difficulties with these kinds of dynamics and this is the reason why for some locations such as Kure Jan strand and Schoorlstrand the percentage of correct predictions is lower than in other locations.

HHNK – 534018 – Twiske – DeDoes – Oostzaan, 2018

Figure V-IV Results of the Algae Radar application to bathing water location De Does (Twiske) for 2018. See Figure V-II for an explanation of the different panels.

HHNK – 534028 – Twiske – DeLeers – Oostzaan, 2018

Figure V-V Results of the Algae Radar application to bathing water location De Leers (Twiske) for 2018. See Figure V-II for an explanation of the different panels.

HHNK – 534003 – Twiske – KureJanStrand – DenIjp, 2018

Figure V-VI Results of the Algae Radar application to bathing water location Kure Jan strand (Twiske) for 2018. See Figure V-II for an explanation of the different panels.

HHNK – 534004 – Twiske – Schoorlstrand, 2018

Figure V-VII Results of the Algae Radar application to bathing water location Schoorlstrand (Twiske) for 2018. See Figure V-II for an explanation of the different panels. Yellow columns indicate the start (and ending) of health warnings by the province.

HHNK – 534026 – Twiske – Speelsloot – L. meer – Den IJp, 2018

Figure V-VIII Results of the Algae Radar application to bathing water location Speelsloot (Twiske) for 2018. See Figure V-II for an explanation of the different panels.

HHNK – 534019 – Twiske – Vennegatstrand – Oostzaan, 2018

Figure V-IX Results of the Algae Radar application to bathing water location Vennegatstrand (Twiske) for 2018. See Figure V-II for an explanation of the different panels.

HHNK – 534016 – Twiske – WezenlijkStrand – Oostzaan, 2018

Figure V-X Results of the Algae Radar application to bathing water location Wezenlijkstrand (Twiske) for 2018. See Figure V-II for an explanation of the different panels.

Table V-II Comparison of Algae Radar predictions with in situ measurements (in relation to Cyanobacteria protocol) at the seven locations in 't Twiske (column 1). The second column shows the amount of data that model and measurements can be compared. The third column shows how often the predictions were in the same health warning level as the measurements.

Location	N	% correct
De Does	10	80
De Leers	9	78
Kure Jan strand	6	67
Schoorlstrand	8	50
Vennegatstrand	11	82
Wezenlijkstrand	11	55
Speelsloot	11	64

V.3. Trasimeno

It is currently not possible to apply the Algae Radar to the WISPStation data because at the time of writing this deliverance we did not have meteorological data of 2018. Since the WISPStation was only installed in 2018, it did not provide data of previous years which is necessary for calibration of the Algae Radar. Therefore, we used in situ measured data for chl-a from ARPA Umbria to calibrate the model for the years 2008-2015 and let the model do predictions for 2016 (which were verified with the in situ measurements of 2016). For Trasimeno, we looked at total chl-a instead of cyanochlorophyll because of lack of data to do the latter. Figure V-XI shows the results of that exercise and Figure V-XII zooms in on 2016. The algal dynamics in Lake Trasimeno differ from the Dutch lakes in the way that Chl-a maxima occur usually later in the year and the growth of almost zero to the maximum runs steeper than in Dutch lakes. This led us to come up with a non-linear approach for the basic model. This included the use of a yearly average (for all days) of Chl-a for the years 2008-

2015 as an extra input for the basic model (next to the meteorological variables). As can be seen in Figure V-XI, the basic model has a good agreement with the measurements. Hence, the adaptive model will then also produce good results. For 2016, 83% of the predictions were in the same health risk level (applying the Dutch cyanobacteria protocol as has been done in Chapters V.1 and V.2).

Figure V-XI Application of the Algae Radar on station TRS35 in Lake Trasimeno. TRS35 is ARPA Umbria station located in the southern east of the Lake. For an explanation of panels and colors of the lines and dots, see Figure V-II. The difference with the cases in the Netherlands is that in Trasimeno Chlorophyll-a was modeled instead of cyano-chlorophyll.

Figure V-XII Algae Radar results for Trasimeno in 2016 (highlighted from Figure V-XI).

Although we could not yet apply the Algae Radar on the WISPStation data in Lake Trasimeno we did a quick exercise to see if the WISPStation produces measurements that resemble the in situ measurements of ARPA Umbria. In Figure V-XIII the daily median chl-a measured by the WISPStation is shown in red. The average yearly in situ measurements of ARPA Umbria are shown in blue (2008-2015). This latter was used as an extra input for the basic model of the Algae Radar (see text above in this Chapter). As for the in situ measurements, the WISPStation also shows that chl-a starts to increase late in the year (between June and July). Figure V-XIII also presents an Algae Radar hindcast for 2010 (black line). The results of this hindcast (2010 was chosen because chl-a levels were also high that year) show that the Algae Radar can produce Chl-a concentrations and dynamics that are in line with measurements in Lake Trasimeno.

Figure V-XIII WISPStation measurements for Chlorophyll-a (red line), average year Chl-a profile (blue line, calculated over the years 2008-2016) and Algae Radar hind cast of 2010 (black line).

V.4. Discussion and conclusions

The AlgaeRadar showed good results for the three lakes. The current version is a seasonal forecasting model. The addition of algal dynamics from the past (as applied in Trasimeno) may be applicable in all lakes to produce a seasonal forecast. For a daily forecast, automated in situ data such as the WISPStation will become important. In 2019, this will be done in lakes Paterswoldsemeer and Trasimeno.

A high advantage of the AlgaeRadar is the quick running time. When input data are ordered in columns setting up the AlgaeRadar for a specific lake can be done within 1-2 days. At this moment, the AlgaeRadar only produces forecasts for the location of the measurements. A 2D model may be considered in lakes for which earth observation data are very frequently available. In these cases, every satellite image pixel may then be used as a data input location and a 2D model version of the AlgaeRadar can then be created.

VI. References

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